

Studies on Hydroxamic Acids : XIV. Reactions of N-Aryl Hydroxamic Acids with Metal Ions*

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N-Phenylbenzohydroxamic acid is now an established analytical reagent¹⁻³. By making structural modifications in its molecule several new reagents, with better analytical properties, have been developed in recent years³⁻¹¹. Recently, the use of 51 N-aryl hydroxamic acids for the solvent extraction and spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) was reported^{1,2}. In the present communication potentially useful analytical reactions of the typical compound, N-*m*-tolyl-*p*-methoxybenzohydroxamic acid(I), with

metal ions are briefly described. The reactions were examined by the procedure of West^{1,3}, and the pH of incipient and complete precipitations, which depend in a large measure on the concentrations of metal ion and the ligand^{1,4}, were estimated approximately. Generally, 1 to 2% w./v. solution of hydroxamic acid in rectified spirit was used for precipitation reaction while for extraction 0.1% w./v. solutions in chloroform was satisfactory. Suitable buffer solutions were used for adjusting the pH. The data on precipitation and extraction of metal ions is given in Table 1. The solvent extraction behaviour of the coloured five membered chelates of vanadium(V), uranyl(II), cerium(IV), titanium(IV) and iron (II and III) is attractively suited for further study. Beryllium(II) and zirconium(IV) chelates are thermally stable and of definite composition and hence these may be useful for gravimetric applications.

In general, all the N-aryl hydroxamic acids reacted in a similar manner with a particular metal ion. Slight

TABLE—1 : PRECIPITATION AND EXTRACTION OF METAL IONS WITH N-M-TOLYL-P-METHOXYBENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID

I Metal ion	II Approximate pH range for extraction and precipitation	III Colour of chloroform extract	IV Colour of the precipitate
Au(III)	4-6	Yellow*	Yellowish brown
Cu(II)	3-6	Green	Green
Be(II)	3.5-7.5	Colourless	White
Al(III)	4-7	Colourless	White gelatinous
Sn(II)	0.3-2.5N HCl	Colourless	White
Ce(IV)	0.02-10N HCl	Yellow	Yellowish white
Ti(IV)	0.02-10N HCl	Yellow	Yellow
Zr(IV)	0.1-4N HCl	Colourless	Grey white
V(V)	2-10N HCl	Bluish-violet	Violet
Mo(VI)	0.1-5M HCl	Yellow*	Yellowish white
U(VI)	1-7	Orange	Orange-red
Pd(II)	4-7	Pink*	No precipitate
Cr(III)	3-5	Yellow	No precipitate
Fe(II)	2-6	Purple	Red
Fe(III)	2-6	Red-Purple	
		Violet	Red
Pt(IV)	4-6	Pink	Yellow

* Better extraction with more concentrated ($\frac{1}{3}$ %) reagent solutions.

variations in colour, pH of incipient and complete precipitations were observed.

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Estimation of Chromate Ions in presence of various Oxy-anions by Polarographic Method

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KOLTHOFF Gregor¹ determined chromate ions amperometrically by titrating it with barium ions in presence of various percentage of ethanol, which lowers the solubility of barium chromate. The present paper presents the results of the polarographic determination of chromate ions in presence of arsenate, arsenite, molybdate, tungstate, bromate, selenate & tellurate ions.

Experimental

Solutions containing various concentration of chromate ions (0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 mM) were prepared in presence of 0.1M concentration of various oxy-anions containing 0.1M NaOH. The above solutions were also prepared in absence of sodium hydroxide and it was observed that in absence of NaOH the reduction waves either contained maxima or ill defined and thus the results were not useful from analytical aspect. The polarograms were recorded on Radiometer P O4 automatically after deaeration for 20 min by bubbling purified nitrogen. The blank polarograms of various oxy-anions in 0.1M NaOH were also recorded to choose the suitability of oxy-anions. All the measurements were carried out at 30°C which was maintained with Haake type ultra thermostat. Electrolysis was carried out in a conventional H-type cell with a agar-agar plug saturated with KCl. The dropping mercury electrode having $m = 1.1464$ mg/sec. and $t = 5$ sec. (at 50 cm of mercury pressure in 0.1M NaOH with applied potential of -1.0 V vs S. C. E.) was used for all the measurements.

Results and Discussion

(i) *Reduction of chromate ions in presence of molybdate ions* : Investigations were carried out in 0.1M molybdate having 0.1M NaOH. Chromate ion produces a single well defined polarographic wave in presence of 0.1M molybdate ions containing 0.1M sodium hydroxide. The i_x was found to increase with increase of chromate ion concentration where as half wave potential remained constant. The plots of i_x vs chromate ion concentration was linear and pass through original. This shows that the reduction of chromate ions is diffusion controlled in presence of 0.1M molybdate in strongly alkaline media. Thus small amount of chromate ions can be determined in excess of molybdate ions. The results have been summarised in Table 1.

(ii) *Reduction of chromate ions in presence of tungstate ions* : In presence of 0.1M tungstate containing 0.1M NaOH, chromate ions produce two reduction waves. The first wave being small and contained a round maxima where as the second wave was found to be well developed having no maxima. Thus the second wave is useful for its determination. Attempts to suppress the maxima for the first reduction wave was not successful with gelatin (0.01%) or triton X₁₀₀

TABLE I—CONCENTRATION OF CHROMATE IONS (MM)

Supporting electrolyte	0.5 E _{1/2} (-V vs S.C.E.)			1.0 E _{1/2} (-V vs S.C.E.)			1.5 E _{1/2} (-V vs S.C.E.)			2.0 E _{1/2} (-V vs S.C.E.)		
	I _d (μA)	I _d /C		I _d (μA)	I _d /C		I _d (μA)	I _d /C		I _d (μA)	I _d /C	
Molybdate	1.085	5.58	11.0	1.090	11.00	11.00	1.080	16.50	11.00	1.080	22.00	11.00
Tungstate	1.080	4.25	8.50	1.080	8.50	8.50	1.080	12.75	8.50	1.080	17.00	8.50
Selenate	1.085	5.00	10.00	1.090	9.75	9.75	1.080	15.00	10.00	1.080	20.00	10.00
Bromate	1.070	5.75	11.50	1.080	11.25	11.25	1.080	17.00	11.30	1.080	22.50	11.20
Arsenate	1.080	9.50	19.00	1.080	18.75	18.75	1.080	28.50	19.00	1.080	38.00	19.00
Arsenite	1.080	4.50	9.00	1.085	9.05	9.05	1.080	13.60	9.06	1.080	18.00	9.00